

THE RELEVANCE OF THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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This article analyzes the current state of the fight against corruption in the higher education system, the factors that determine its relevance and influence it, and the changes in the field in recent years.

Key words: corruption in the higher education system, the basis of the relevance of the issue, corruption-free sphere.

In recent years, important organizational and legal reforms have been implemented in the field of fighting corruption in our country. Systematic measures are being taken to increase the legal consciousness and culture of the population, to form an intolerant attitude against corruption in the society.

Creating a corruption-free society and state will be a solid guarantee of the country's development. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the ceremony dedicated to the 26th anniversary of our Constitution on December 7, 2018, stated that "We will never achieve our goals with corruption"

All reforms directed by the state against corruption are carried out for the rights and interests of citizens.

Special attention is being paid to the training of independent thinking, high moral and ethical qualities, competitive personnel by forming an intolerant attitude towards corruption, especially in the field of education.

In particular, in his address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, the President said, "We must create all the facilities for the education of our enthusiastic young people who want to get a higher education, work on themselves and become knowledgeable. Therefore, we will increase the level of coverage of school graduates with higher education to at least 25% in 2020 and 50-60% in the future", they emphasized.

According to the analysis provided by the Jaxon Bank, the development of the labor market in our country is taking place along with the changes in the economy, which leads to an increase in the

demand for various professions, and the importance of quality higher education in meeting the demands of the labor market. it is recommended to implement according to the changes.

We can determine that the fight against corruption in the higher education system is an urgent issue by various factors, but the following factors are the most important:

1) in a situation where the types of professions in the modern state administration and the private sector are rapidly increasing, the demand for qualified personnel is increasing and the use of mature personnel services is of crucial importance in achieving positive results;

2) to be a highly educated person in order to live comfortably in the conditions of today's market economy, to have professional and human respect;

3) serious negative consequences resulting from the interference of corruption in the relations between the parties based on the two factors mentioned above.

The demand for qualified personnel in the public and private sector and the desire to obtain material and moral benefits by obtaining a higher education have a strong influence on the growth of relations between entities and the transformation of legal relations into corrupt relations. After all, the fact that getting a higher education and becoming a qualified employee requires hard work, and not everyone can achieve it with their own strength and ability, encourages them to use the method of corruption.

According to the first basis, the state's high attention and need for higher education is also proven by the figures below.

Today, there are 178 higher education institutions (hereinafter HEIs) in the Republic, which are 34 universities, 48 institutes, 3 academies, 1 conservatory, 33 non-state higher education institutions, 27 branches, 31 foreign institutions and are their branches. By the end of the 2021/2022 academic year, 808,400 students are studying in them.

During the last three years, more than 200 legal documents were adopted in the higher education system. During this period, 6 higher education institutions, 17 branches, 14 foreign higher educational institutions were established in our country, personnel training was launched in more than one hundred bachelor's and 94 master's courses, from the 2019-2020 academic year, 59 higher education institutions offer part-time education and 10 evening education. was

introduced. The number of HEIs is 117-increased to 178. As a result of these measures, the level of coverage of young people with higher education increased from 9% to 20%.

The amount of funds allocated to the industry from the budget is increasing year by year, and in 2018 it reached 879 billion. 1 trillion soums in 2019. 288 billion soums of funds were allocated, this year this figure is 1 trillion. 888 billion amounting to soum. The salary of professors and teachers was increased by 25% on average in 2018, but it was increased by 20% from January 1, 2019, and by 25% from July 1 [5]. Starting from 2022, up to 15% bonus payment was introduced for teachers according to the qualification category. It is also planned to increase the monthly salary of teachers to 1,000 US dollars by 2025.

According to the second basis, higher education stands out as an important area in the fight against corruption, because higher education is the final stage of continuing education leading to employment. The demand for higher education is very high all over the world and in our country, and the strong competition in this field increases the possibility of corrupt situations.

If we turn to the numbers, in the field, in 2019, 1,066,922 candidates, including previous graduates, took the entrance exams to OTM, 121,000 of them were recommended for studentship, while in 2022, 1,146,744 candidates (increased by 9.3%) expressed their desire to study at OTM, registered and made up 121,395 of the state orders for admission to state higher education institutions. This is an indicator without taking into account the number of students admitted by 64 non-state and foreign higher education institutions and their affiliates.

It can be seen that the level of admission of candidates to the state higher education institution is 10.5 percent.

According to the third basis, higher education is the "primary school of corruption", because in this activity the student, as an independent adult, engages in direct illegal activity with the teacher, and in it a personality prone to corruption is formed [6]. In the future, taking a responsible position of a corrupt person will cause negative consequences. Therefore, the presence of corruption in higher education paves the way for corruption to spread to other areas. Corruption in the field creates uneducated demands, and the example of an infectious disease encourages educated students to choose the path of corruption.

Finally, it will be possible to easily divert the young generation, who lacks sufficient knowledge and skills, from the state policy, lead them to various negative paths, and this, in turn, will have a negative impact on the political and moral situation in the state.

Taking into account the important factors mentioned above, the state is paying attention to higher education as one of the most important areas, and intensive reforms are being implemented in order to make it a truly "corruption-free area".

Article 11 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" dated September 23, 2020 states that higher education provides training of highly qualified specialists [8].

Accordingly, the Decree No. PF-5847 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" [9], it was determined to introduce effective mechanisms to fight corruption and ensure transparency.

Also, in the Decree No. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", on the basis of the introduction of international standards for the assessment of the quality of education and training, improving the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions, gradually increasing admission quotas to higher education institutions if multiplication is specified, On the basis of Resolution PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country", a "roadmap" was created for the reforms to be implemented in the higher education system. Decree No. PF-5763 dated June 11, 2019 "On measures to reform management in the field of higher and secondary special education" provides for the creation of an effective management system in the higher education system.

In addition, based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 27, 2019 "On measures to further improve the system of fighting corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-5729, it was decided to implement the "corruption-free sector" project in the higher education system as an experiment from August 1, 2019.

From 2021, the "compliance-control" system of combating corruption was introduced in higher education institutions, and

systematic work on corruption cases in this field and its prevention was launched.

Despite the special attention and care paid to the higher education system by the head of our state, cases of corruption, serious problems and defects remain in the field. Therefore, first of all, it will be necessary to identify the existing corruption risks in the higher education system and eliminate them.

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